

Original Article

ACQUISITION OF DIGITAL SKILLS BY ACCOUNTING EDUCATION STUDENTS IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES FOR EFFECTIVE PERFORMANCE IN ENUGU STATE.

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Abstract

The study determined Accounting Education student's opinion on the acquisition of Digital skills by Accounting Education students in public universities for effective performance in Enugu State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested. The population of the study comprised 35 Accounting Education students from two government owned Universities (UNN and ESUT). The instrument was a-24 item structured questionnaire developed by the researcher entitled: Acquisition of Digital skills by Accounting Education students in Public Universities for effective performance Questionnaire (AODSBAESIPUFEPQ). The instrument was duly validated by three experts. The reliability was done using Cronbach Alpha which yielded coefficient of 0.94, indicating the instrument was reliable. The two research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation (SD) were used to determine the homogeneity and closeness of the responses. While, the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistics. Results of data analysis relating to the study have shown that Microsoft Excel skills and SPSS skills are digital skills acquired by Accounting Education students in public Universities for effective performance in Enugu state. The hypotheses tested, showed that there was no significant difference between the Accounting Education students in Federal and State universities regarding the acquisition of Microsoft Excel skills and SPSS skills for effective Performance respectively. Based on the findings, it was recommended that Institutions should offer hands-on training sessions using real-world accounting software like QuickBooks, Excel, SPSS, Access and Tally. This can be achieved through lab sessions, workshops, or simulation-based learning, enabling students to practice and develop their digital skills actively.

Keywords: Acquisition, Digital skills, Accounting Education students, Universities and effective Performance.

Introduction

The word digitalization is now a household name in the present society. Moreover, it is observed that technological advancement has taking over different aspect of work and life at large. The rapidly changing global environment provides both opportunities and threats. The 21st century is

characterized by the advancement of technologies, Chuquimarca and Bedón, (2020), which makes digital literacy essential for individuals to access information and knowledge either for opportunities or be aware of threats. According to Ugwunwoti (2021), the information revolution coupled with the

attendant technologies has changed the nature of business and its operations. When there is digitalization of economy, it directly affects the nature of business, employability and society, especially of students in full vocational training who, if not, will soon enter the field of work.

The ability to use various digital technologies or applications, and the knowledge of various networks to manage and access information is referred to as digital skill. It enables people to create, share digital content, communicate, collaborate, and solve problems. A typical example of this multidimensional concept is the Information and Communication Technology, which has created new global networks, dismantling national boundaries and barriers, thereby generating a global village where one can access information from any part of the universe within seconds (Olaniyi, 2015). It is on note that, the COVID-19 lockdown measures have made digital skills even more relevant. The use of digital technologies has substantially increased, largely as many people now work, learn from home, manage health, social life, and household chores (e.g., shopping) in a digital environment. At the same time, the COVID-19 pandemic revealed gaps in digital skills as well as the existing risks and limited knowledge in using a range of digital technologies for different purposes.

During the lockdown in 2020, teachers, parents, and students found remote schooling extremely challenging, partly due to their low level of digital skills (not to mention the inequalities in access to digital devices and infrastructure Carretero (2021). It is not an overstatement to state that, digital skills are changing the way people work in recent times, revealing opportunities and risks. Millions of jobs are at risk of being replaced with automation, especially jobs that involve repetitive, routine tasks (Gonzalez-Vazquez, 2019). In as much as jobs could be replaced by automation due to digitalization, the fact cannot still be denied that digital skills could increase employability and earnings. A considerable

number of companies, particularly large companies with more than 250 employees, need digitally competent workers. Curtarelli (2017) illustrated that almost 60% of employers in large firms believed some of their staff were not fully proficient in digital tasks, while less than a quarter of employers at small firms (10 to 249 employees) expressed the same concern. Moreover, workers with moderate or advanced use of ICT have a higher probability of having high-paid jobs, compared to those with little or no use of ICT. For effective performance to be achievable by the Accounting Education students there is needed to acquire digital skills.

Skill is proficiency in performance that may be enhanced by practice and training (Chell, 2013). Similarly, Eya and Ugwunwoti (2021) described skills as the ability to do something well, usually gained through training or experience that is needed. Ugwunwoti (2023) opined that, skill is the learned ability to perform an action with determined results with good execution often within a given time, energy or both. If any skill is to be needed for effective performance, it is digital skills.

Digital skills are the abilities to use digital devices, communication application and networks to access and manage information. According to Umoru (2019) digital skills referred to as skill related to use technology. Moreover, according to Cornell University Digital Literacy Resource (2019), digital skill is the ability to find, evaluate, utilize, share and create content using technologies and the internet.

International Finance Corporation (2019) predicted that over 230 million jobs in sub-Saharan African will need digital skills by 2030. The World Bank Group office, Ghana (2019) opined that, a global digital revolution is underway and likely to bypass Africa. No wonder, World Bank (2018) stated that, digital skill is a driver of economic growth and competitiveness. Hence, the need for the digital skills for Accounting Education students.

Digital skills are the driving forces for innovative, inclusive and sustainable growth through innovations

and digitalization which in turn stimulate job creation, alleviate poverty, reduce inequality, and facilitate the delivery of goods and services (ILO, 2021). The digital skills meet young people's intrinsic value to a specific occupation and they open doors to acquire extra knowledge, skills and qualifications (ILO, 2021). Promoting the acquisition of digital skills alongside lifelong learning can help unemployed workers of all ages to take up new occupations in which more jobs are available (ILO, 2021). Digital skills are previously portrayed as essential skills to an unemployed and employed people in the labour market as they are proved to be needed in almost all primary and managerial occupations (Curtarelli, 2017; Andrews, 2018; Mwakatumbula & Moshi, 2020). The digital skills have thus increasingly attracted the greater interest of non-employed and employed people; and employers in the labour market. Digital Skills are essential for inordinate opportunities in economic growth and improvements in working conditions of the labour market (Morandini, 2020). The digital skills are exceedingly treasured in the modern workplace, digital skills are highly valued and the treasure of the given skills will be more stressed and vital in the future (The UK's Digital Future, 2015). The digital skills are nowadays expanding into all aspects of lives apart from IT area hence should be taught as one of the generic skills with the same importance as other skills like numeracy and literacy (Whitehead, 2014). This means that, digital skills are entering all areas of work including medicine, entertainment, communication, marketing, and education, Business Education inclusive.

Business Education on the other hand is one of the occupational areas that are richly provided by vocational and technical education in Nigeria. Major topics in Business Education include: Office Practice, Book Keeping, Business Mathematics, Business Communication, secretarial duties, word processing, advertising (Ajisafe, Bolarinwa & Edeh 2015). Edokpolor and Egbri (2017) had stipulated

that the actual goals of Business Education shall be to: prepare students for specific career in office occupations, equip students with the requisite skills for job creation and entrepreneurship, and expose students with knowledge about business, including a good blend of computer technology, which incorporates Information and Communication Technology (ICT). They further explained that the first two goals involve education 'for' business, which is aimed at equipping recipients with the requisite attributes (digital skills, knowledge, competencies, and attitudes) to become gainfully employed in the world of work, whereas the later addresses education 'about' business, which is aimed at providing a sound basis for further studies at the graduate and post-graduate levels. This study sees Business education as a programme of instruction that offers various skills in Entrepreneurship, Marketing, Office Technology and Management (OTM) and Accounting Education.

Accounting is one of the most important courses in Business Education, with initiation of nationalization and indigenization policy, the demand for accountant has continued to increase tremendously, hence the importance attached to it. Similarly, Accounting Education is a vocation which prepares one for skillful and gainful employment as one of the Business/vocational Education courses. It is a known fact; that Accounting Education is one of the major options in Business Education. Accounting Education is one of the courses offered in Nigerian Universities which prepares its recipients for careers in Accounting and Education (Ugwunwoti and Nomeh, 2016). Accounting Education is an option in Business Education. Nwokike (2010), opined that, Accounting Education is the type of education that provides individuals with skills and knowledge in accounting, computing and data-processing occupation for gainful employment in private and public enterprises for self-employment. The end products of Accounting Education programme for the graduates are to be Accounting teachers,

Accountants, Bookkeepers, Cashiers, Clerks among others. The Accounting Education students while in universities are expected to acquire needed digital skills for effective performance on graduation.

University Accounting Education students are learners who are undergoing formal four years programme in the Accounting and Education. Such learner is expected to have a Bachelor of Science in Accounting Education. Accounting Education students are expected to acquire relevant skills while in classrooms. However in this context, they are expected to acquire Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) and Microsoft Excel.

Microsoft Excel is a foundational tool for accountants, and proficiency in Excel is often considered a basic requirement for accounting roles (Eze, 2016). Thus, accounting students acquiring Excel skills during their university education is a significant step toward self-employment. Microsoft Excel provides powerful tools for data analysis, allowing students to efficiently process and interpret large datasets (Okafor, 2017). Functions such as sorting, filtering, and pivot tables enable the extraction of meaningful insights, essential for research projects, lab reports, and assignments. Excel is extensively used for data analysis, financial modelling, and generating reports (Machera, 2017). For accountants or those starting their own accounting firms, the ability to analyze and present financial data is crucial for providing valuable services to clients. Excel is instrumental in financial planning, budgeting, and forecasting. Accountants often need to assist clients in creating budgets, projecting financial outcomes, and making informed financial decisions. Excel's automation features, including formulas, functions, and macros, enhance efficiency in managing financial data. Accountants can streamline their processes, reduce errors, and handle a higher volume of work with these automation tools. Excel facilitates clear communication with clients through visual representations of financial data. Graphs, charts, and

tables created in Excel help convey complex information in an understandable manner, fostering effective collaboration between accountants and clients. Accountants need to make strategic business decisions for their practice. Excel equips them with the tools to perform business analysis, assess profitability, and make informed decisions to grow their entrepreneurial ventures (Ravi, 2018).

Excel skills acquired during university education are transferable across various industries. Accountants might find opportunities in diverse sectors, ranging from traditional accounting services to consulting, financial analysis, or even entrepreneurial ventures. Clients often expect a high level of professionalism from their accountants. Proficiency in Excel enhances the quality of financial services, instills client trust, and contributes to the accountant's reputation in the market. Excel is continuously evolving, and new features are regularly introduced. Accounting Education students acquiring Excel skills during their university studies are better positioned to adapt to technological changes, ensuring they remain competitive in the self-employment landscape. The acquisition of Microsoft Excel skills by Accounting Education students at universities is vital for their journey toward self-employment. Excel proficiency not only enhance learners marketability but also equips them with essential tools for providing high-quality accounting services and managing their own entrepreneurial endeavours effectively as well as SPSS.

SPSS, which stands for Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, is a powerful software tool widely used for statistical analysis in various disciplines. Originally developed for social science research, SPSS has evolved to become a versatile tool employed in fields such as psychology, health sciences, business, and education. It allows researchers and analysts to explore and interpret data, making it an indispensable resource for making informed decisions based on empirical evidence. SPSS enables users to efficiently manage and

manipulate data. With features for data entry, cleaning, and transformation, it facilitates the organization of datasets for analysis. The core strength of SPSS lies in its extensive array of statistical procedures. From descriptive statistics to advanced analyses such as regression, ANOVA, and factor analysis, SPSS provides a comprehensive suite of tools for exploring relationships and patterns within data (Amesur, 2016).

In the business world, SPSS aids in market research, customer analytics, and decision-making processes by providing insights derived from data analysis. SPSS is employed in finance and economics for tasks such as risk analysis, financial forecasting, and economic modelling. SPSS is a versatile and powerful tool that empowers researchers, analysts, and decision-makers to derive meaningful insights from data. Its applications span across diverse industries, making it a valuable asset for those seeking to unlock the potential within their datasets and make data-driven decisions. As technology continues to advance, SPSS remains a relevant and indispensable tool which professionals engaged in statistical analysis and research. When these skills are acquired by Accounting Education students, it will enhance their effective performance.

Effective performance is the cornerstone of success in any endeavour, whether it is in academics, professional pursuits, or personal development. It encompasses the ability to set and achieve goals, excel in tasks, and continually improve one's skills and competencies. Effective performance refers to the ability to achieve desired outcomes or goals efficiently and successfully. It involves the demonstration of competence, productivity, and effectiveness in completing tasks, projects, or responsibilities within a given context (Wahida 2021). Effective performance begins with clearly defined objectives. Whether short-term or long-term, specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) goals provide a roadmap for

success. Clarity of purpose allows individuals to focus their efforts and resources efficiently.

Effective performance refers to the execution of tasks and responsibilities by an individual in a setting. It is a crucial dependent variable in organizational psychology and behavior, driving the entire economy (Campbell & Wiernik, 2015). Work performance can be influenced by various factors, including human resource practices, training, performance appraisal, career planning, and employee participation and technology (Irshad 2021). Digital skills can be used to improve effective performance in various ways, which were found in several previous studies. Digitalization transfer and human resource development skills can enhance the effective performance of extension agents towards sustainable beekeeping production among bookkeepers. (Isah, 2019). Telework tasks and workplace suitability can have a positive relationship with collaboration and effective performance, especially when communication technology is emphasized (Müller, 2021). The integration of recent smart technologies with the human factor can contribute to employees' involvement at the shop floor level and thus improve quality control (Silva, 2021). A person who has acquired requisite skills in the course of training in educational institution through acquisition of digital skills is expected to perform effectively. It is therefore the responsibility of Business Educators in Federal and State universities to improve the digital skill levels of Accounting Education students which will in turn ensure that their skills and knowledge are fit-for-purpose for the labour market upon graduation. Federal universities are owned, financed and controlled by the Federal government. Similarly State universities are owned, financed and controlled by the State Government. Nigeria as a nation and Enugu State in particular will enjoy sustainable development if Accounting Education students in particular and all other students in general acquire maximum skills in their specialties which will enable

them to be gainfully employed or become employers of labour.

According to Aliata and Hawa (2014), several changes have taken place in private and public offices as regards the functions and responsibilities of Accounting Education graduates. Therefore, the acquisition of digital skills by Accounting Education students cannot be over-emphasized. To fit evenly into the world of office works today, public universities should develop the students theoretically and practically in digital skills needed to practice as accountants, office managers and entrepreneurs upon graduation. It is against this backdrop that research on acquisition of digital skills by Accounting Education students in public universities for effective performance will be carried out.

According to Nwazor (2021), emerging trends in learning and teaching to include that responsibility for learning should lie with the students, not the teachers where the students will be part of setting the objectives or goals of learning and determining the assessment standard. This means that the level of performance of Accounting Education students upon graduation depend largely on the level of skills acquired while in school.

Statement of the Problem

In today's rapidly evolving technological landscape, the integration of digital skills is crucial for professional success, especially in fields like Accounting. Accounting education students in public universities are expected to be equipped with the necessary digital skills to navigate the dynamic demands of the modern workforce. However, there is a pressing need to investigate the extent to which these students acquire digital skills and whether they are adequately prepared for effective performance and self-employment opportunities in the digital era. The problem arises from the potential gap between the traditional curriculum of Accounting education and the evolving technological requirements of the contemporary job market. As the business environment increasingly relies on digital tools and

technologies, accounting professionals need to possess a broad spectrum of digital skills, including but not limited to data analysis, financial software proficiency, cyber security awareness, and digital communication abilities. The relationship between quality of skills possessed by Accounting Education students upon graduation and the labour market has been the focus of growing theoretical and empirical investigations in the education literature. The Employers views of how well Accounting Education graduates are prepared for the workplace have received widespread attention in the education sector. The attention is connate because if Accounting Education graduates do not acquire these relevant digital skills, they would not fit-in the labour market driven by technological advancement. Therefore, there is need to reverse the trend by finding out the needed digital skills, hence, the following question, what then are these digital skills? Finding answer to this question is the major concern of this study.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the extent of acquisition of digital skills by Accounting Education students in public universities for effective performance in Enugu state. Specifically, the study sought to determine extent of acquisition of:

1. Microsoft Excel skills by Accounting Education students in public universities for effective performance in Enugu state.
2. SPSS skills by Accounting Education students in public universities for effective performance in Enugu state.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the extent of acquisition of Microsoft Excel skills by Accounting Education students in public universities for effective performance in Enugu state?
2. What is the extent of acquisition of SPSS skills by Accounting Education students in public

universities for effective performance in Enugu state?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. H_{01} . There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Accounting Education students in Federal and those in State universities in Enugu State on the extent of acquisition of Microsoft Excel skills for effective performance.
2. H_{02} . There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Accounting Education students in Federal and those in State universities in Enugu State on the extent of acquisition of SPSS skills for effective performance.

Method

A descriptive survey research design was employed in this study. According to Nworgu (2015) descriptive survey, is the one in which a group of people is studied by collecting and analyzing data from few people considered to be representative of the entire group. The study was carried out in two Government owned Universities in Enugu state (University of Nigeria, Nsukka and Enugu state University of Science and Technology). The population for the study comprised of 29 Accounting Education students from University of Nigeria, Nsukka and 6 from Enugu state University of Science and Technology respectively totaling 35 Accounting Education students. There was no sampling, because the population size was manageable.

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher entitled: Extent of Acquisition of Digital skills by Accounting Education students in public Universities for effective performance Questionnaire (AODSBAESIPUFEPQ). The instrument has three sections. Section A was on bio-data. Section B on the Microsoft Excel skills and section C contains items on SPSS skills. The rating responses were Very High Extent (VHE) High Extent (HE) Low

Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) with numerical value of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was validated by three experts. Two from the Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education and one from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education (Measurements and Evaluation) both from Enugu state University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu State. To test the reliability of the instrument, 20 Accounting Education students in government owned Universities in Ebonyi State was used. Cronbach Alpha estimate was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument; which yielded a coefficient index of 0.94. This index indicated that, the instrument was reliable enough to be used for the study.

The researchers with the help of three research assistants used direct delivery techniques in the administration of the instrument to the respondents. At the end of the administration of the instrument, all the 35 copies were returned and used for the study; representing 100% rate of return. Mean and standard deviation was used in answering the research questions; while t-test was used in testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance at the appropriate degree of freedom

Decision rule for answering the research questions was based on the real limits of the mean this:

Very High Extent - 3.50 - 4.00

High Extent - 2.50 - 3.49

Low Extent - 1.50 - 2.49

Very Low Extent - 1.00 - 1.49

For the hypotheses, when the calculated t-value was equal to or greater than the table value, the null hypotheses was rejected, otherwise it was rejected.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What is the extent of acquisition of Microsoft Excel skills by Accounting Education students in Public Universities for effective Performance in Enugu state?

Table 1: Mean scores and Standard deviation on the extent of acquisition of Microsoft Excel skills by Accounting Education students in Public Universities for effective Performance in Enugu state.

S/N	Items statements on Microsoft Excel skills	Federal N=29		State N=06		Overall N=35		Decision
		X1	SD1	X2	SD2	X	SD	
1	Create new workbook	3.43	0.76	3.31	0.76	3.37	0.76	HE
2	Create a formula	2.89	1.03	3.62	1.23	3.26	1.13	HE
3	Find numbers in a workbook	3.17	0.84	3.15	0.87	3.16	0.86	HE
4	Create result sheet	3.29	0.85	3.35	0.78	3.32	0.82	HE
5	Navigate a worksheet	3.09	0.90	3.27	0.71	3.18	0.81	HE
6	Insert rows in a worksheet	3.38	0.58	3.25	0.85	3.32	0.67	VHE
7	Create budget consolidation	3.48	0.62	3.38	0.72	3.43	0.67	VHE
8	Edit cell contents	3.31	0.73	3.21	0.80	3.36	0.77	VHE
9	Perform calculations	3.25	0.75	3.35	0.62	3.30	0.69	HE
10	Insert blank cells in a worksheet	3.42	0.50	3.49	0.71	3.49	0.61	VHE
11	Prepare stock inventory	3.05	0.96	3.18	0.81	3.12	0.87	HE
12	Prepare bank statements	3.48	0.50	3.49	0.71	3.49	0.61	VHE
	Cluster mean/SD	3.27	0.75	3.34	0.68	3.31	0.72	VHE

The results in Table 1 shows that, the respondents (Accounting Education students) in Federal and State universities in Enugu state have the overall mean scores ranges from 3.12 to 3.49; indicating that the 12 items were Microsoft Excel skills acquired by Accounting Education students in Public Universities for effective Performance in Enugu state. The overall cluster was 3.31 indicating agreement. The lower cluster standard deviation of 0.72 showed that, the respondents had similar views

on the items as the extent of acquisition of Microsoft Excel skills by Accounting Education students in Public Universities for effective Performance in Enugu state.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Accounting Education students in Federal and their counterparts in State universities in Enugu state on the extent of acquisition of Microsoft Excel skills for effective Performance.

Table 2: Summary Table of t-test of mean scores of Accounting Education students in Federal and those in State Universities on the extent of acquisition of Microsoft Excel skills for effective Performance in Enugu state.

Accounting Education students	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
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Federal	29	3.27	0.75				
				33	0.04	1.96	NS
State	06	3.34	0.68				
	35						

Table 2 Showed that, the calculated t-tables at 0.05 level of significance and 33 degree of freedom was 0.04, while critical t-value under the same conditions was 1.96. Since the calculated t-value was less than the table-value, the null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. This invariably means that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of Accounting Education students in Federal and those in State universities in Enugu state on the extent of

acquisition of Microsoft Excel skills for effective Performance.

Research Question 2

What is the extent of acquisition of SPSS skills by Accounting Education students in Public Universities for effective Performance in Enugu state?

Table 3: Mean scores and Standard deviations of the respondents on acquisition of SPSS skills by Accounting Education students in Public Universities for effective Performance in Enugu state

S/N	Items statement on SPSS skills	Federal		State		Overall		Decision
		N=29		N=06		N=35		
		X1	SD1	X2	SD2	X	SD	
13	Ability to input data	3.56	0.69	3.51	0.71	3.50	0.70	VHE
14	Ability to manage data	3.44	0.66	2.75	0.77	3.10	0.72	HE
15	Ability to transform data	3.23	0.79	3.21	0.75	3.22	0.77	HE
16	Proficiency in applying various statistical techniques available in SPSS	3.28	0.72	3.52	0.54	3.40	0.63	VHE
17	Capability to interpret and analyze output generated by SPSS	3.30	0.73	3.19	0.75	3.29	0.74	HE
18	Creating informative and visually appealing graphs to present data effectively	3.20	0.79	3.12	0.82	3.16	0.81	HE
19	Familiarity with writing syntax commands in SPSS to perform advanced data manipulations	2.86	0.97	2.92	0.96	2.89	0.97	HE
20	Understanding of survey data analysis techniques	3.15	1.03	3.49	0.71	3.32	0.89	HE
21	Knowledge of advanced statistical techniques	3.20	0.73	3.19	0.72	3.19	0.73	HE
22	Ability to critically evaluate research questions	3.08	0.91	3.29	0.74	3.19	0.83	HE
23	Understanding how to integrate SPSS with other software tools such as Microsoft Excel, word etc	3.60	0.66	3.52	0.77	3.56	0.72	VHE

24	Ability to import data	3.20	0.79	3.12	0.82	3.16	0.81	HE
	Cluster mean/SD	3.25	0.79	3.24	0.82	3.25	0.81	HE

The result in Table 3 above showed that item 13, 19 and 23 with mean scores of 3.50, 3.89 and 3.56 have a very high extent. Similarly, the result equally showed that, items 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 20, 21, 22 and 24 with mean scores of 3.10, 3.22, 3.40, 3.29, 3.16, 3.32, 3.19 and 3.16 respectively have agreed to high extent responses. This means that Accounting Education students in Federal and State owned universities were in agreement that acquisition of

SPSS skills will enhance effective Performance in Enugu state; The low standard deviation (0.81) shows similar views of the respondents.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Accounting Education students in Federal and those in State universities in Enugu state on the extent of acquisition of SPSS skills for effective Performance

Table 4: Summary Table of t-test analysis of mean scores of Accounting Education students in Federal and State owned universities in Enugu state regarding the extent of acquisition of SPSS skills for effective Performance.

Accounting Education students	No	\bar{x}	SD	df	t-table	t-cal	Decision
Federal	26	3.25	0.79	33	1.11	0.96	Do not reject HO
State	06	3.24	0.82				
	35						

Table 4 Showed that, the calculated t-table at 0.05 level of significance at 33 degree of freedom was 1.11; while the critical t-value under the same conditions was 1.96. Since the calculated was less than the table value, the null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. This means that, Accounting Education students in Federal and State owned universities in Enugu state did not differ significantly in their mean scores on extent of acquisition of SPSS skills for effective Performance.

Discussion of Findings

The data presented in Table 1, showed that Accounting Education students in Federal and State universities in Enugu state were in agreement that Microsoft Excel skills were acquired by Accounting Education students in Public Universities for effective Performance in Enugu state. The findings are in line with Okafor, (2017), that Microsoft Excel provides powerful tools for data analysis, allowing

students to efficiently process and interpret large datasets.

The null hypotheses one tested on the Microsoft Excel showed that, there is no significant difference in the items on the mean scores of Accounting Education students in Federal and State owned Universities in Enugu state on the extent of acquisition of Microsoft Excel skills for effective Performance. This indicated that the university type of the respondents have no significant influence to the identified Microsoft Excel skills acquired for effective performance.

Data obtained regarding research question two, revealed that Accounting Education students in Federal and State universities in Enugu state were in agreement that, SPSS skills are acquired by Accounting Education students in Public Universities for effective Performance in Enugu state. The findings of the study were in line with the

findings made by Amesur, (2016), that SPSS enables users to efficiently manage and manipulate data.

The null hypotheses two tested, showed that Accounting Education students in Federal Universities and their counterparts in State type did not differ significantly in their mean scores on acquisition of SPSS skills for effective Performance in Enugu state. The indication of the findings was that the university type has no influence to the identified SPSS skills acquired for effective performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it implied that the extent of acquisition of Microsoft Excel skills and SPSS skills were greatly acquired by Accounting Education students in public universities in Enugu state. The findings of the study therefore, have shown that acquisition of digital skills by

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Accounting Education students in public universities was at a high extent.

Respondents (Accounting Education students in Federal and State owned Universities) were equally of the view that there was no significant difference in the means scores regarding Microsoft Excel skills and SPSS skills respectively are acquired by Accounting Education Students in public universities for effective performance in Enugu State.

Recommendations

Based on the Findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

1. Institutions should offer hands-on training sessions using real-world accounting software like QuickBooks, Excel, SPSS, Access and Tally.
2. Universities should invest in digital infrastructure, such as modern computer labs, up-to-date accounting software licenses, and online learning platforms.

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